

THE « MARSH » DATABASE : NEKTON COMMUNITY STATUS IN TWO TIDALLY RESTORED MARSHES FROM THE GIRONDE ESTUARY, SOUTHWEST FRANCE.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Natural intertidal marshes display paramount ecological functions as transition systems between marine and freshwater environments on the one hand, and between aquatic and terrestrial systems on the other hand. These ecological functions are mostly supported by an intensive primary and secondary productivity, including detritic production, and by marshes' morphological and structural habitat diversity. Intertidal marshes and adjacent mudflats also represent important nursery areas, i.e., feeding and growth habitats, for juveniles of many fish and macro-crustacean species (Kneib, 1997). Accordingly, intertidal marshes are considered essential habitats for sustaining adult fish and crustacean populations in coastal marine environments (Boesch and Turner, 1984), among which populations of species supporting fisheries of significant economic value in Europe, such as European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax* Linnaeus, 1758), Thin lipped mullet (*Liza ramada* Risso, 1826), sardine (*Sardina pilchardus* Walbaum, 1792) and grey shrimp (*Crangon crangon*, Linnaeus, 1758) (Cattrijsse and Hampel, 2006).

Despite their recognized ecological importance, natural intertidal marshes severely regressed at a global scale. In Europe in particular, coastal marshes were massively dyked over almost a millennium, mostly with the purpose of increasing agricultural land surface. This process of dyking coastal marshes and building damming systems to drain the lands gained on the sea is designated in Europe as 'polderization', from the deutsch term 'polder', as the Netherlands historically initiated the engineering expertise on coastal marsh dyking. This historical polderization of coastal wetlands resulted in the creation of approximately 15,000 km² of littoral polders in Europe (Goeldner-Gianella, 2007).

This polderization process however stopped around the 1970s, concomitant with the adoption by many countries of the Ramsar convention on wetlands in 1971. More recently, in some countries of western Europe and north America, an inverse trend is even being observed : some polders are given back to estuaries or coastal seas. This is done sometimes accidentally through the impact of storms on deteriorated or poorly managed dykes, and sometimes deliberately through concerted restoration actions. In Europe, this tendency is nowadays designated through the term 'depolderization', which includes both accidental and deliberate cases (Goeldner, 1999; Verger, 1993). Few of those cases actually benefit from scientific surveys aiming at monitoring the impact of depolderization on ecological functionalities of restored marshes.

When implemented, monitoring programmes often take place during the first years following the restoration of the marsh, with the duration of surveys typically limited to five years (Simenstad and Thom, 1996). The nekton in

particular has been scarcely analyzed in the context of marsh restoration operations (French, 2006), and the few studies available were conducted in the United-States with very rare case studies in Europe (Colclough et al., 2005). This is partly due to methodological issues related to nekton sampling in marshes where environmental conditions strongly fluctuate, and where habitat conditions and accessibility of sampling sites evolve very quickly (Rozas and Minello, 1997).

In the Gironde estuary, two marshes were tidally restored accidentally, and supported nekton monitoring programmes since 2008 : the Mortagne-sur-Gironde marsh and the north part of the Nouvelle island. The Mortagne-sur-Gironde marsh is located on the right side of the mesohaline section of the Gironde estuary. Covering 191 hectares, it was dyked in 1966 and used for agricultural harvesting for more than 30 years. Its protective dyke broke off during a storm in December 1999. The north Nouvelle island marsh is located in the oligohaline section of the estuary. Its protective dyke also broke off accidentally during a storm in 2010.

Biological monitoring programmes were conducted in these two marshes between 2008 and 2016, in order to assess if the depolderization process resulted in the restoration of marshes nursery function for estuarine and coastal fishes and macrocrustaceans. The 'MARSH' database gathers all information collected during those surveys (from 2008 to 2016), including nekton samples.

2. MAIN FEATURES AND POTENTIAL USE OF THE DATABASE

The database identifies all technical data related to sampling methodologies (fishing techniques, conditions and dates), as well as characteristics of the samples collected (taxa, fish abundance and weight, and individual length and morphometric dimensions).

The data can potentially be used to :

- describe nekton assemblages characterizing dyked marshes and natural intertidal (natural marshes and mudflats) and subtidal areas in a macrotidal estuary;
- compare nekton assemblages among anthropized, restored and natural habitats within the same estuary;
- study the temporal dynamics of nekton assemblages in tidally restored marshes;
- study the size distribution of several species (e.g. *Liza ramada*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*, *Pomatoschistus microps*, *Palaemonetes varians*, *Palaemon longirostris*) within diked and other intertidal habitats of the Gironde estuary;
- study length-weight relationships of multiple fish and macrocrustacean species.

3. STRUCTURE OF THE DATABASE

3.1. GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Fishes and crustaceans (crabs, shrimps, crayfish) are collected in the field with a specific fishing gear. A *fishing operation* therefore corresponds to the use of a particular fishing gear in a defined spatial (*site*) and temporal (*campaign*) context, which results into the collection of a sub-set of individuals from multiple species present in the natural environment, this sub-set being referred to as a biological *sample*.

All individuals composing those biological samples are identified to the lowest taxonomic level possible (species the most often), counted, and measured. Those measurements are done directly on the field for large-sized individuals (length > 60-70 mm), or back at the laboratory for smaller individuals. In the case of very abundant species, only a sub-set of individuals is being measured. Besides length, other morphological characteristics are sometimes measured or noted, for example individual weight, sex or the presence or absence of eggs (for shrimps).

Based on this protocol, for a given fishing operation, a same species can appear in both the sample fraction directly processed on the field, and in the sample fraction processed back at the laboratory (which is being frozen for archiving purpose). In some instances, this same species can also be sub-divided in the database into categories of size, in order to keep track of potential differences in sub-sampling procedures applied to each of these size fractions. For example, sub-categories « *Dicentrarchus labrax* L > 60 mm » and « *Dicentrarchus labrax* L < 60 mm » can be recorded within the same fishing operation.

Two types of fishing operations are distinguished : *stationary* and *trawled* operations. Stationary fishing operations are performed at a recurrent and fixed location identified as a fishing *station*. Several replicates (i.e., fishing operations realized at a similar period and location) are often associated to a same fishing station. Fishing stations are characterized by their fixed geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude). Trawled fishing operations are mobile events, relying on the use of trawled fishing gears which trajectory (or *trawl lines*) cannot be exactly replicated. Trawled fishing operations are described by polylines with coordinates achieved at successive times.

Abiotic environmental measures are also collected during fishing operations : water height (for intertidal and dyked areas) or depth (for subtidal areas), water temperature and salinity, etc. For stationary fishing operations, abiotic variables are measured either directly at the fishing station, or at a close location that can be common to several stationary fishing stations. Water height is often specifically measured for each stationary fishing operation replicate (as replicates can be realized at different times). For each trawled fishing operation, abiotic factors are usually averages of several measures collected along the trawl line.

Fishing operations can be performed in the context of different research projects. Each research project (e.g., « capalest », « ile_nouvelle ») is structured in several sampling campaigns (e.g., « capalest_may11 », « ilenouv_may11»). Each fishing operation can therefore be associated to one or several fishing campaigns (as associated to one or several research projects). For instance, fishing operations conducted at the 'Ile Nouvelle' site in May 2011 are associated to both May 2011 campaign of the « ile_nouvelle » project (« ilenouv_may11 » in the database) and at the May 2011 campaign of the « capalest » project (« capalest_may11 »).

3.2. DATA SETS

The MARSH database comprises data produced by several research projects conducted between 2008 and 2016. The sampling protocols have evolved over time during this period, with protocols being described in several reference documents (Table 1).

Table 1: List of reference documents describing sampling protocols used to produce the MARSH database

Project	Period	Reference documents	Comments
Margo	2008-2009	(Decreton, 2009; Lechêne, 2017)	The database structure described in Decreton (2009) has been fully revised
Ile Nouvelle V0	2009-2013	(Chapalain, 2013; Lechêne, 2017, 2015)	Only fishing data collected between 2011 and 2013 were used in Lechêne (2017)
Remob	2010-2012	(Lechêne et al., 2011, 2012)	-
Capalest	2011-2012	(Rimond, 2013; Lechêne, 2017; Lechêne et al., 2018b)	-
Renomares	2013	(Carlu, 2013)	Training period realized at the 'Conservatoire du Littoral' and 'Conservatoire Régional des Espaces Naturels' (CREN) Poitou-Charentes, in partnership with Irstea
Marino	2016	(Allou, 2016)	Training period realized at the 'Conservatoire du Littoral' and 'Conservatoire Régional des Espaces Naturels' (CREN) Poitou-Charentes, in partnership with Irstea

3.2.1 GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION

Fishing operations associated to GPS coordinates are illustrated in Figure 1. A total of 90 fishing stations and 100 trawls are included in the database.

Figure 1: Fishing operations included in the MARSH database.

3.2.2 NUMBER OF FISHING OPERATIONS BY RESEARCH PROJECT

Fishing operations, as included in the database, correspond to the association between a fishing station or trawl line, a fishing gear, and a date. Therefore, if a fishing operation is conducted by two fishing gears, two records will appear in the database. The number of fishing operations for each research project is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Number of fishing operations for each research project included in the MARSH database, considering fishing gear used.

Project	Number of fishing operations
Capalest	757
Ile_nouvelle_v0	340
Margo	36
Marino	70
Remob	259
Renomares	154

A total of 133 fishing operations are common to projects « Capalest » and « Ile_nouvelle » (64 in 2011 and 69 in 2012). The total number of fishing operations is therefore 1 483 (and not 1 616 that would correspond to the addition of numbers from Table 1).

The actual number of fishing operations, without considering fishing gear used, sums to 1 009, distributed as in Table 3.

Table 3: Actual number of fishing operations for each research project, without considering fishing gear used.

project	Number of fishing operations
Capalest	485
Ile_nouvelle_v0	222
Margo	36
Marino	12
Remob	254
Renomares	76

The database comprises 8 620 samples (taxon × fishing operation combination), associated to 98 different taxa. A total of 80 823 biological specimens are identified and individually recorded, essentially for body length measurements.

Fishing operations cover a period from 2008 to 2016, with a frequency illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Monthly distribution of fishing operations included in the MARSH database

3.3. DESCRIPTION OF TABLES

3.3.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DATABASE

Illustration 3: Structure of the database

3.3.2 THE « CAMPAGNE » TABLE (CAMPAIGNS)

Table of fishing campaigns

Field	Type	Definition
campagne_id	Varchar	Campaign code, made of two elements : a mnemonic chain reminding the project name, month (3 characters) and year (2 characters). Example : <i>ilenouv_May11</i>
fk_projet_id	Varchar	Project identification code, in chain form

3.3.3 THE « ECHANTILLON » TABLE (SAMPLES)

List of samples collected, ordered by taxa or taxa subtypes

Field	Type	Definition
echantillon_id	Integer	Counting type key
fk_operation_peche_id	Varchar	Fishing operation reference
fk_taxon_id	Varchar	Taxon reference
Soustype	Varchar	For some taxa and fishing operations, individuals are distributed in different categories or subtypes (onto-genetic stages, size classes, etc.)
nt	Numeric	Total number of collected individuals
nm	Numeric	Number of individuals with any measurement or determination (e.g., length, weight, sex determination, etc.)
np	Numeric	Number of individuals with body weight measurement
mt	Numeric	Total weight (g) of the sample (note: many records in the database result from calculations rather than direct measurements)
Commentaire	Varchar	Comment regarding the sample

3.3.4 THE « H_EAU » TABLE (WATER HEIGHTS)

Table of water heights

Field	Type	Definition
h_eau_id	Serial	Incremental key
fk_operation_peche_id	Varchar	Fishing operation
dateh	Timestamp	Measurement date and time
h_eau	Numeric	Water height (m) between bottom and surface

3.3.5 THE « INDIVIDU » TABLE (INDIVIDUALS)

List of biological individuals collected

Field	Type	Definition
individu_id	Integer	Counting type key
fk_echantillon_id	Integer	Sample reference
lf	Numeric	Fork length (mm)
lt	Numeric	Total length (mm)
lst	Numeric	Standard length ¹ (mm)
lflt	Numeric	NULL – not informed ²
lct	Numeric	<u>For shrimps</u> : post-orbital cephalothorax length « Lct » (mm) <u>For crabs</u> : maximal cephalothorax width (mm)
m	Numeric	Individual weight (g)
sexe	Char(1)	Individual sex, if known – 2 possible values : <i>m</i> for male, <i>f</i> for female
ov	Boolean	Spawning status – 2 possible values : TRUE (bear eggs) or FALSE (do not bear eggs) Only informed for shrimps

¹ Fish length measured from the snout to the end of the notochord

² Field not informed anymore, but kept in the table structure to avoid revision in R or SQL extraction scripts

3.3.6 THE « MESURE_PARAMETRE » TABLE (MEASUREMENT PARAMETERS)

Table of physico-chemical variables associated to fishing stations

Field	Type	Definition
mesure_parametre_id	Serial	Incremental key
libelle_mesure	Varchar	Measurement code, made of a station abbreviation (fk_station_id), month/year and optional complementary information Example : <i>christoly_oct11_smp2_p2</i>
fk_station_id	Varchar	Station code
Dateh	Timestamp	Date-hour of measurement
heau	Numeric	Water height (m) between bottom and surface
heau_sonde	Numeric	Water height (m) above the pressure sensor of the probe
temperature	Numeric	Temperature (°C) measured by the probe in air or water (see « milieu » field)
conductivite	Numeric	Conductivity (mS/cm)
conductance_sp	Numeric	Specific conductance (mS/cm) at 25°C As conductivity measurements depend on temperature, specific conductance corresponds to a « corrected » conductivity measure allowing the comparison of waters with different temperature
salinite	Numeric	Salinity (no unit)
milieu	Varchar	This field specifies if the probe is immersed in water (value = « eau ») or emerged in the air (value = « air ») at the time of measurement. If this information is not available, the value is NULL. This field is needed in cases when measurement probes are installed on stationary locations submitted to tidal influences. To select values collected at high tide only (when the probe is immersed in water), select values == « water »

3.3.7 THE « OPERATION_PECHE » TABLE (FISHING OPERATIONS)

List of fishing operations

Field	Type	Definition
operation_peche_id	Varchar	Fishing operation code, made of a location abbreviation, month and year, and informations about the fishing gear Example : <i>t1_medoc_mar11_hav_tribord</i>
fk_station_id	Varchar	<u>For stationary fishing operations</u> : fishing station reference <u>For trawled fishing operations</u> : value = NULL
fk_trait_id	Varchar	<u>For stationary fishing operations</u> :value = NULL <u>For trawled fishing operations</u> : trawl line reference
engin	Varchar	Fishing gear used
nb_engin	Numeric	Number of fishing gears used to collect the biological sample When the two parts of double fykes are considered separately, nb = 0.5
dateh_debut	Timestamp	Date and hour of fishing gear deployment
dateh_fin	Timestamp	Date and time when fishing gear stops operating

Field	Type	Definition
cim	Numeric	Immersion coefficient This field only concerns samples collected with double fykes. The immersion coefficient (cim) is a ratio varying from 0 to 1, corresponding to the proportion of the fishing period during which the fyke is immersed allowing the sampling of aquatic organisms. See Lechêne (2017).
volfil	Numeric	Filtered water volume (m ³) This field only concerns some specific fishing gears : winged fyke net, push-net or frame net (Rimond, 2013).
longueur	Numeric	Trawl line length (m) This field only concerns trawled fishing operations
surface	Numeric	Sampled surface (m ²) This field only concerns trawled fishing operations
commentaire	Varchar	Comment on the fishing operation

3.3.8 THE « PROJET » TABLE (PROJECTS)

List of projects codes included in the database

Field	Type	Definition
projet_id	Varchar	Project code, from the following list : - margo - ile_nouvelle_v0 - remob - capalest - renomares - marino

3.3.9 THE « STATION » TABLE (STATIONS)

List of fishing or measurement stations

Field	Type	Definition
station_id	Varchar	Station code
type_station	Varchar	Two possible values : « peche » (=fishing) or « mesure » (=measurement) A fishing station is a station which is associated with stationary fishing operations (table « operation_peche ») and physico-chemical measurements (table « mesure_parametre »). A measurement station is a station with only physico-chemical measurements (table « mesure_parametre »).
lat_wgs84	Float	Latitude (decimal) in WGS 84 reference (EPSG: 4326)
long_wgs84	Float	Longitude (decimal) in WGS 84 reference (EPSG: 4326)

3.3.10 THE « TAXON » TABLE (TAXA)

List of biological taxa

Field	Type	Definition
taxon_id	Varchar	Taxon Latin name, in the form genera_species (when known) Examples: <i>Abramis_brama</i> , <i>Abramis_sp</i>
nom_commun_taxon	Varchar	Taxon French common name. Spaces are replaced with ‘_’
code_taxon	Char(6)	Code used to abbreviate the names of taxa
genre	Varchar	Taxonomic genera, in Latin

Field	Type	Definition
famille	Varchar	Taxonomic family, in Latin
ordre	Varchar	Taxonomic order, in French
sousclasse	Varchar	Taxonomic subclass, in French
classe	Varchar	Taxonomic class, in French
sousphylum	Varchar	Taxonomic subphylum, in French
groupe	Varchar	Taxonomic group, in french
gilde_ecologique	Varchar	Ecological guild, in French Examples : « especes_migratrices_amphihalines » (diadromous species), « especes_marines_stenohalines » (marine stenohaline species)
longueur_type	Varchar	Indicates the length measurement type to select for the taxa of interest (either fork length « lf », total length « lt », or length or width of cephalothorax for crustaceans « lc »)

3.3.11 THE « TRAIT » TABLE (TRAWL LINES)

List of trawl lines for trawled fishing operations

Field	Type	Definition
trait_id	Varchar	Trawl line reference, composed of the date and a code of fishing zone Example : 2011-03-01_maubert_saintonge_tr1
profondeur	Numeric	Average depth (m) along the trawl line
profondeur_sonde	Numeric	Average depth (m) at which the probe measuring physico-chemical parameters is being installed during the trawl line
temperature	Numeric	Refer to table « mesure_parametre »
conductivite	Numeric	Refer to table « mesure_parametre »
conductance_sp	Numeric	Refer to table « mesure_parametre »
salinite	Numeric	Refer to table « mesure_parametre »

3.3.12 THE « TRAIT_GEOM » TABLE (GEOMETRIC LINES)

GPS coordinates measured along trawl lines

Field	Type	Definition
trait_geom_id	Serial	Automatic key
fk_trait_id	Varchar	Trawl line reference
ordre	Integer	Measurement point order along the trawl line
dateh_gps	Timestamp	Date-hour of measurement point
lat_wgs84	Float	Latitude (decimal) in WGS 84 reference (EPSG: 4326)
long_wgs84	Float	Longitude (decimal) in WGS 84 reference (EPSG: 4326)

4. DATA ACCESS AND DATA POLICY

Data are provided in SQL format (export from Postgresql 9.5), allowing for their identical recovery. Data are published under *Open Licence*³, with compulsory mention of data producer at export : Irstea – 50 avenue de Verdun – 33612 CESTAS Cedex – France. Data freely downloadable at : <https://www.zenodo.org/record/1413514>

³ https://www.etalab.gouv.fr/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/Open_Licence.pdf

5. CONCLUSIONS

The MARSH database represents a unique source of information regarding the dynamics of nekton assemblages in restored marshes of Mortagne-sur-Gironde and Ile Nouvelle, and in the Gironde estuary in general. The large number of observations collected within a relatively short period of time in multiple habitats indeed allows for a complete picture of the Gironde estuary status. Several scientific publications are based on those data (Lechêne et al., 2018a, 2018b), including a PhD dissertation in 2017 (Lechêne, 2017).

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